

METHODS OF IMPLEMENTATION OF INFORMATION PROTECTION SYSTEM

Orinboyev Alisher Shavkatjonovich

Students of the Fergana branch of TUIT named after Muhammad Al-Khwarizmi

Annotation: In this article, legal methods of information protection and the main directions of security for electronic computing. In addition, it provides information about the type of confidential information and the principles of their operation.

Keywords: ISAF, information security, technical, computer systems, personnel, confidential information, computer systems.

AQQQT is created to protect information security at facilities from a number of potential threats. A specific set of protection methods and tools is used to block this or that threat. Some of them protect information from multiple threats at the same time. Among the methods there are also universal methods, which are the basis for any protection system.

These are legal ways of protecting information, which serve as the basis for the formal construction and use of a voluntary duty protection system;

these are organizational methods that are typically used to eliminate (reverse) multiple risks;

these are technical methods that protect information from most threats based on organizational and technical measures.

Legal issues in the legal methods of information protection include:

- Development of penalties for computer crimes;
- protection of programmers' copyrights;
- Improving criminal and civil law, as well as litigation in the field of computer crime;

ISSN (E): 2181-4570 ResearchBib Impact Factor: 6,4 / 2023

- issues of public control over the developers of computer systems;
- adoption of relevant international agreements on these issues, etc.

Considers organizational measures for information protection:

- protection of computer systems;
- selection of employees;
- Denial of the fact that the most important work is carried out by only one person;
- the presence of a plan to restore the system's ability to function after its failure;
- giving responsibility to those who provide information security systems;
- selection of the location of the computer center, etc.

The basic laws define the purposes, concepts and legal bases of information and information resources.

The Law "On Information, Informatization and Protection of Information" provides for the constitutional right of citizens to information, its openness and access to it, information on the legislative, executive and judicial bodies by citizens and organizations, etc. encourages access to information, the provision of public and private interest, and the promotion of communication and the development of information in society. It deals with the documentation of information and its relevance to the categories of open and limited access to information resources, the definition of mechanisms and powers to access information, the order of legal protection of information, the mechanisms of liability for violations in this area.

Objectives of protection of information defined by law:

- Elimination of theft, vandalism, embezzlement, forgery;
- ensuring the security of the individual, society and the state;
- Elimination of prohibited actions for loss, violation, blocking of information;
- protection of the constitutional rights of citizens to privacy and confidentiality of personal data;

ISSN (E): 2181-4570 ResearchBib Impact Factor: 6,4 / 2023

- protection of state secrets, confidentiality of documented information.

The law defines the objects of information security, which include:

- 1) all types of information resources;
- 2) the rights of citizens, legal entities and the state to receive, disseminate and use information, protect confidential information and intellectual property;
- 3) systems of formation, distribution and use of information resources, including information systems of different classes and functions, information libraries, archives, systems and large collections of information technology regulations and processes of information collection, processing, storage and transmission scientific, technical and service personnel;
- 4) information infrastructure, including information processing and analysis centers, mechanisms for ensuring the operation of information exchange and telecommunication channels, telecommunication systems and networks, including information protection systems and tools;
- 5) public consciousness based on mass media and propaganda (worldview, moral values, moral values, socially acceptable stereotypes of behavior and human relations). By law, restricted access messages are protected and the level of protection is determined by their owner, and the responsibility for safeguards rests not only with the owner but also with the user. Only documented information is protected. Documented information is divided into state secrets and classified information.

State secrets include state-protected military, foreign policy, economic, intelligence, counterintelligence, and operational search activities. The owner and user of these messages will be the state itself, so it will put forward protection requirements and oversee their management. Violation of these requirements is punishable by all strict laws.

Confidential information is documented information, the legal regime of which is established by special norms of the current legislation in the field of state, commercial, industrial and other public activities. The owners are the institutions and organizations that have access to and act on this information, and they set the level of

ISSN (E): 2181-4570 ResearchBib Impact Factor: 6,4 / 2023

protection. In the event of a breach of confidentiality, certain sanctions may be imposed only if the following formalities have been completed in advance:

- the information must be really valuable;
 - the institution should take certain measures to deny free access to information and to protect its confidentiality;
 - All employees must be informed about the confidentiality of information.
- introduction of content management system
- Experimental verification of the developed system functions

The object of research is an electronic document management system

The research topic is management documentation

Research methods include:

- 1) methods of working with electronic documents;
- 2) methods of information retrieval, processing and storage;
- 3) methods of automating the solution of various functions of office work;
- 4) methods of data mining;
- 5) methods of checking the value of electronic documents.

The theoretical basis of the study was:

- documentation of local and foreign research management activities on labor organization;
- An enterprise that uses electronic document management with modern concepts that reveal the essence of modern activities.

When the theoretical and practical significance of the work is developed, the electronic document management system can be combined with the content management system, ending with a commercial proposal and implemented in the enterprise.

List of used literature

1. Akbarov D. E., Umarov S. A. Mathematical characteristics of application of logical operations and table substitution in cryptographic transformations //Scientific-technical journal. – 2021. – Т. 4. – №. 2. – С. 6-14.
2. Акбаров Д. Е., Умаров Ш. А. Алгоритм электронной цифровой подписи на основе композиции вычислительных сложностей: дискретного логарифмирования, разложения на простые множители и сложения точек эллиптической кривой //Автоматика и программная инженерия. – 2020. – №. 2 (32). – С. 29-33.
3. Умаров Ш. А., Умарова М. И. ПОНЯТИЕ О ДРЕВОВИДНЫХ СТРУКТУРЫ ДАННЫХ //Интернаука. – 2021. – №. 5-1. – С. 9-12.
4. Guo P. et al. Surface self-reconstruction of telluride induced by in-situ cathodic electrochemical activation for enhanced water oxidation performance //Applied Catalysis B: Environmental. – 2022. – Т. 310. – С. 121355.
5. Тожибоев И. Т. Краевые задачи в специальной области для уравнения смешанного типа //Вестник Томского государственного университета. Математика и механика. – 2018. – №. 56. – С. 17-28.
6. Mirzapolatovich E. O., Eralievich T. A., Mavlonzhonovich M. M. Analysis of Static Characteristics Optoelectronic Level Converters Liquids and Gases Based on Hollow Light Guides //EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 6. – С. 29-31.

